

Dynamic Load Resistance Verification and Finite Element Modelling of Confined Masonry Using Shock Table Experiments

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Abstract

Earthquakes causes most of loss of life that occurs due to collapse of buildings, constructed in traditional materials like stone, bricks, wood, etc, which are not particularly engineered to be earthquake resistant. In view of the continued use of such buildings in most countries, it is very much essential to introduce earthquake resistant features in their construction.

Masonry buildings are generally categorized as “Non Engineered Constructions”. These are built by following traditional practices without detailed structural analysis. Normally masonry structures are subjected to vertical loads and since masonry has adequate compressive strength, the structure performs well as long as the loads are vertical. When such a structure is subjected to lateral inertial forces during an earthquake, the wall develops shear and flexural stresses. The strength of masonry under these conditions purely depends on the bonding between masonry units and mortar, which is quite poor. Hence these constructions are inherently weaker for resisting earthquake forces.

It is reported by Coburn and Spence (2002) that almost 75% of the fatalities, attributed to earthquakes in the last century, is caused by collapse of buildings of which the greatest proportion (more than 70%) is due to collapse of masonry buildings. A majority of the tenements in India are URM buildings that are weak and vulnerable even under moderate earthquakes. On the other hand, a cursory glance through the literature on earthquake resistant structures reveals that a bulk of research effort is on RC structures. Clearly there is a great need to expend more effort in understanding masonry buildings subjected to earthquake induced dynamic loads.

Keywords: *Earthquake resistant design, Masonry Buildings, Shock table studies.*

Introduction:

Masonry is the most important construction material. It has been used for public and residential buildings in the past several thousand years. A great number of well-preserved old masonry structures still exist proving that this form of construction can successfully resist loads and environmental impact. Masonry has been popular through the ages for its fire resistance, its thermal capacity and its durability. However, the combination of weight, stiffness and weakness against tensile forces makes traditional masonry buildings highly vulnerable to earthquakes.

However, in the last few decades, considerable research on the behavior of masonry walls and buildings subjected to seismic actions has been carried out in many countries. Use of strong mortars, high strength masonry, added reinforcement, improved detailing and the introduction of good anchorage between masonry walls and floors and roofs have enhanced the resistance of masonry to seismic stresses. These improvements enable the masonry building to act as a box-type structure. Vertical gravity loads are transferred from the floors and roof, which act as horizontal tension elements, to the bearing walls, which support the floors and act as vertical compression members. During earthquakes, however, floors and roofs act as horizontal diaphragms that transfer the seismic forces, developed at floor levels, into the walls. In addition to this, floors and roofs connect the structural walls together and distribute the horizontal seismic forces among the structural walls in proportion to their lateral stiffness.

Recent Studies on a few publications on earthquake resistant masonry, from different parts of the world. It must, however, be mentioned that the quantum of research is not commensurate with the extent of the damage to masonry subjected to earthquake. A representative list of publications on such masonry is discussed here. The first portion of this survey deals with the Indian context while the next part deals with the investigations carried out elsewhere.

A report by Shradha Navalli (2001) refers to the practice in Uttaranchal where they use horizontal timber bands at different levels to improve the integrity of the masonry structure. Such houses suffered little damage during the October 1991 Uttarkashi earthquake. The paper by Jai Krishna and Arya (1962) also refers to such practices.

In an attempt to evaluate the seismic behaviour of masonry with different earthquake resistant features, the concept of **shock table** testing was developed. The shock table is a simpler version of a full-fledged shake table facility. In case a specific structure is responding in the inertial mode it is predominantly sensitive to acceleration and hence a shake table can be justifiably replaced by a shock table, which is subjected to base impacts. This can also be used to compare the behaviour of geometrically similar models and thus find the efficacy of different earthquake resistant features.

Jai Krishna and Sekaran (1962) first developed a pendulum impact table. Later, Keightley (1977) worked in Roorkee using a wagon moving down an incline to generate shock loading. Arya (1995) applied this concept in a shock table testing of masonry models subjected to moving tractor impacts. These studies showed the improved performance of masonry when provided with a horizontal belt of reinforcement at lintel level.

More studies in this line were carried out by Rajendra Desai and Jagadish (1999) at Latur where a series of four shock-table testing involving eight different models were undertaken.

Saikia (2002) conducted two shock table studies on a 1/4th scale model and 1:2.5 scale model, using a pendulum impact device. These studies also showed the value of horizontal reinforcement bands at lintel and roof levels.

Agarwal and Thakkar (1998, 2001) carried out a series of shock table tests and quasi- static tests on masonry building models. The tests were intended to study the strengthening and retrofitting measures in masonry buildings, particularly the efficacy of seismic bands and corner reinforcements. They have reported

that the portion of the wall between the bands fail in brittle shear while the out-of-plane response is considerably improved.

Bruneau (1994) makes a number of observations on the seismic performance of un-reinforced masonry buildings (URM). Some of the types of failures are listed as

- Lack of anchorage between floor and walls
- Anchor failure when joists are anchored to walls
- In-plane failure
- Out-of-plane failure
- Combined in-plane and out-of-plane effects

Among these he emphasises that URM buildings are most vulnerable to *flexural out-of-plane failure*. In-plane failure may not right away lead to collapse since the load carrying capacity of a wall is not completely lost by diagonal cracking. However, out-of-plane failure leads to unstable and explosive collapse. Sometimes an initial in-plane failure may weaken the wall and subsequent out-of-plane motion can lead to collapse.

The Bureau of Indian Standards came up with a code of practice for Earthquake Resistant Design and Construction of Buildings IS: 4326 (1993). This code incorporated the results of some of the earlier studies of Roorkee and the traditional practices in Quetta, Kutch and Uttarkashi. The essential features of the code recommendations are

- i. The use of lintel and roof/floor bands of RC which tie all the walls together
- ii. Specifications for locations of door and window openings to avoid weakening of walls
- iii. Vertical reinforcement in corners and Tee junctions of walls and at jambs of door and window openings

“Brick Masonry Building Model with Seismic Bands under the Action of Base Motion”, carried out by Mr. Rakul Remanan, PG student of UVCE, BU, submitted during March 2001, sponsored by KSCST. This investigation was conducted to evaluate the behaviour of masonry buildings with horizontal bands alone.

“Seismic Evaluation of Corner and Containment Reinforcement for Masonry Buildings”, carried out jointly by Mr. Sunoj, Mr. Vinod, Ms. Shantha and Ms. Monica, at the UG level at BMSCE, Bangalore. This project was submitted during June 2002 (sponsored by KSCST). In this investigation the effectiveness of the corner reinforcement vis-à-vis a new concept of ‘containment reinforcement’ developed by Jagadish (Professor, Dept of Civil Engineering, IISC, Bangalore-12.) was evaluated. The size of the model was increased to 1:2.5 scale but in spite of providing the corner reinforcement, corner separation was observed.

“Shock Table Studies for Corner Strengthening of Masonry Buildings”, carried out by Ms. Shantha Rashmi, at PG level during July 2005 (sponsored by KSCST). The corners of a masonry building, which are highly vulnerable during lateral loads, gets separated rather easily. In this project, the effectiveness of a special type of corner strengthening scheme using containment reinforcement, was studied on the 1:2.5 scale

model. Here English bond wall was adopted for the building model. This was compared with the corner reinforcement suggested by IS-4326 (1993). It was observed that the corner strengthening using containment reinforcement proved to be highly effective in mitigating corner damage.

Objectives of the present work:

In the present investigation, the concept of “confined masonry”, as reported in many western literatures, is being evaluated for its seismic performance. Again, the models are of 1:2.5 scale and has been tested using the shock table facility with base impacting device.

The main objectives of the study are:

- a. To understand the performance of “Confined Masonry”
- b. To study the failure / crack patterns of “Confined Masonry”
- c. To understand the interaction of the confining elements (RC) with neighboring masonry panels
- d. Comparison of the behavior of Confined Masonry with the other seismic resistant systems such as containment reinforced masonry.

Methodology

“Confined Masonry” is a construction system where masonry wall panels are confined on all the four sides with reinforcing elements such as RC. The confining elements are **not** intended to enhance the vertical or horizontal load carrying capacity of the structure. On the other hand, it is intended to enhance/impart ductility and structural integrity of masonry. Hence the confining elements are not designed as moment resisting frames. The confining elements shall be constructed with minimal disturbance to the process of wall construction. It is proposed to provide the vertical confinement by allowing a gap in the wall, which houses the vertical reinforcement. The gap shall later be filled with rich mortar or concrete with high fine content.

As in the past the building models constructed on the shock table shall be subjected to a series of controlled base shocks using a pendulum-impacting device. The response of the building model shall be observed and monitored using accelerometers mounted at various locations and connected to high speed data acquiring systems.

Construction and Performance aspect of Confined Masonry

The masonry wall panel consists of masonry units bonded with mortar; the masonry units themselves are usually concrete blocks or clay bricks. The elements confining the masonry panel are nearly always constructed of reinforced concrete (RC), although timber and other materials have been used occasionally. In some cases, the units in a masonry wall are staggered or “toothed” at tie column locations (as shown in Figure 3.1) to create better interlock between the wall and tie column.

In a confined masonry system, the masonry wall panels are relied upon to transmit all lateral loads, including earthquake loads, and gravity loads to the building foundation. The bond beams and tie columns work to hold the wall together under earthquake shaking and distribute out lateral load within and between wall panels. The RC confining elements also help improve wall-to-wall, floor-to-wall and roof-to-wall connections, enabling the structure to better act together as a unit during a seismic event. The net effect of the presence of confining members is that confined masonry wall systems have somewhat higher strength and considerably higher deformation capacity than unreinforced masonry wall systems. This translates into better seismic performance.

Figure 3.1 illustrates a typical confined masonry wall.

The masonry walls perpendicular to the direction of shaking are much weaker and more flexible than the walls parallel to the direction of shaking, roof and floors. As a result, these walls transfer their inertial forces to the much stiffer elements bordering the walls. This force transfer is accomplished by out-of-plane bending, which is bending that result in the wall deforming perpendicular to the plane of the wall.

The roof and floor of confined masonry buildings transmit the inertial forces from their own mass, along with the forces transferred to them from the walls perpendicular to the direction of shaking, to the walls parallel to the direction of shaking. To do so, roofs and floors deform inplane (since all deformations are parallel to the plane of the roof or floor) as a diaphragm, and as a result, are referred to as diaphragm elements.

Experimental Studies:

The shock table used for the experiment was a rectangular channel frame of dimension 1.83×1.38m c/c and the cross sectional dimension was 0.15×0.75×.006m. The underneath of the table was fitted with grooved wheels, mounted on bearings so that it allows the motion of the shock table in one direction only. Rails were of inverted T-section. These two rails were anchored to the rigid masonry foundation and the base concrete.

Shock table studies on model 1 –

The size of the model was 1.83m x 1.38m x 0.90m with a wall thickness of 90mm. A 5mm mortar thickness was used for both horizontal and vertical joints. The disposition of the openings were as for a normal box type masonry one room construction that is a door and a window on the cross wall and two windows on the other cross wall. The door opening was 22.5cm x 55.0cm and the window opening was 22.5cm x 28.0 cm. The scaled model was constructed using small sized stabilized mud blocks (soil stabilized with cement). These blocks were prepared using cement, soil and sand in proportion of mix of 1cement: 6soil: 7sand was adopted with water/cement ratio of 1:4. The size of the each scaled brick 115mm x 75mm x 50mm in length, breadth and height respectively. The mould is shown in Fig 4.1 was used to prepare 16 bricks at a time. Blocks were cured for a period of 28 days before using for construction of model.

Table 4.1: Properties of the masonry

Particulars	Model
Wet Compressive strength of brick (MPa)	3.17
Dry Compressive strength of brick (MPa)	5.3
Mortar type	1:10:20 (cement : lime : sand)

Geometric properties	
Length(m)	1.83
Width(m)	1.38
Height (m)	0.9
Wall thickness(m)	0.075
Mass density(kg/m³)	1850
Natural frequencies(Hz) of model 1	27.5

Construction of Model-1: (Confined Masonry)

Model-1 was constructed with three reinforced concrete bands provided at sill, lintel and roof level and also reinforced concrete columns were provided near the openings and also at the corners. The reinforcement for the columns consisted of four no's of 3mm GI rods. The corner columns were of size 75×75mm and the intermediate columns were of size 75×50mm. The reinforcement was anchored to the base by bending it to the L-shape, the horizontal leg being embedded into the channel. Cement mortar (1:4) was filled in the channel to the full depth. Since this model replicated the English bond, it was possible to take the reinforcement through the perpendicular joints at the corners. The reinforcement was filled in cement mortar 1:4 all along the height. One course of blocks was half embedded into the mortar. The blocks were pre wetted prior to usage. Plumb and level were thoroughly checked after each course. Cement mortar was used for the first course to increase the shear strength and thus avoid un-realistic base shear cracks. However lime mortar (1:10:20) was used for the subsequent courses. A steel doorframe and window frame were used for openings on cross wall while two more such window openings were provided in the other cross wall. The first course was almost inside the channel and the doorframe was kept above the first course. Sill band of 1:4 cement mix, which simulated micro concrete, was constructed above the fourth course. It was of 10mm depth and 75mm width. Construction was carried out up to the 4th course (sill level). Above the sill band the window frames were placed. No openings were provided in the shear walls. Then another five courses were laid above which the lintel band was cast as before. Reinforced lintel band was provided after the 9th course. The reinforcement for the bands consisted of GI wires of thickness 3mm and it was held in place by equally spaced 2mm diameter stirrups as shown in the plates and after the 14th course the roof band was provided in the same manner as the lintel band. The thickness of these reinforced bands was 10mm.

Figure 4.4: Placing of the Reinforcing bars

Figure 4.5: Details of Shear Connectors

Figure 4.6: Construction of Sill Band

Figure 4.7: Lintel Band Reinforcement

Figure 4.8: Completion of Lintel band

Figure 4.9: Model after completion of Roof Band

Figure 4.10: Model after White Wash

Figure 4.11: Model with the Pendulum

Base impact test

The model was subjected to a series of base shocks using a pendulum of mass 80 kg. As the angle of release increases the intensity of impact increases, thus the energy imparted increases. The length of the pendulum was 1.5m. It was possible to control the energy imparted to the shock table by changing the angle of release of the pendulum.

Before conducting the test, the model was whitewashed on all four sides of the walls both Inner and outer, to facilitate the observation of cracks. The RC-bands were painted with cement slurry to highlight the bands. Rails and the wheels were greased thoroughly. Accelerometers were attached to both north (shear wall) and west (cross wall) walls just below the roof level. Free vibration test was performed before the impact test. For the impact test, base impact was given by releasing the load from pre-determined distance. This was done to simulate the effects of an earthquake in a realistic manner. During each impact accelerations were recorded using a data acquiring system. The cumulative energy imparted during each impact along with the observed damages during successive shocks is presented in Table 4.2. The following steps show how the energy is being calculated:

Length of the pendulum (L) = 1.50m

Mass of the pendulum (m) = 80kg

Knowing this, the height of the release (h) of the pendulum is calculated

So, the velocity of the pendulum as it strikes the shock table, $V = \sqrt{2gh}$ (m/sec)

Using the principle of impulse momentum, energy is given by, $E = \frac{1}{2} mv^2$ (N-m)

Figure 4.37: After 83 Impacts

Figure 4.38: After 100 Impacts

Figure 4.37: After 145 Impacts

Figure 4.38: After 150 Impacts

The major objective of the test carried out on the masonry model with confining RC elements was to evaluate its seismic performance. Based on the shock table test carried out, it may be concluded that this model satisfies all the requirements of performance. There were no observations of any of the modes of collapse that masonry buildings undergo during earthquakes. The only distress observed was the local failure of some portion of the masonry panel between the confining elements below the sill band. This local failure may be attributed to the high intensity shocks repeatedly given on one side of the table.

Finite Element Analysis

In an attempt to obtain the natural frequencies and mode shapes a finite element model of the building was made and Eigen value analysis was carried out. In the present investigation the masonry building was modeled using four noded shell elements to discretize the walls and the RC slab. A commercially available FEA package, NISA, has been used for the present investigation. This software has been supported with a user-friendly pre-processor and a post-processor. The parameters used for modeling the FE model are summarized in Table 5.1

Table 5.1 - Details of model parameter for FE analysis

<i>Material property</i>	<i>Masonry wall</i>	<i>Confining RC elements</i>
Element type	4 noded orthotropic shell element	2 noded 3D beam element
Poisson's ratio μ	0	0.1
Modulus of elasticity E	1000.00	8000.00 (for 1:4 CM)
Density kg/m^3	20	2500

Figure 5.1 shows the geometry of the FE model. Fig 5.2 shows the isometric view of the FE model and Fig 5.3 shows the plan view of the FE model. Fig 5.4 shows the realistic plot of confined masonry FE model. Fig 5.5 to 5.7 shows the first three mode shapes of the confined masonry model.

Figure 5.4: Geometry of FE Model

Figure 5.4: Isometric View

Figure 5.3: Plan View

Figure 5.4: Realistic Plot of Confined masonry FE Model

Figure 5.5: First Mode Shape

Figure 5.6: Second Mode Shape

Figure 5.7: First Mode Shape

Experimental Results:

An Eigen value analysis was carried out on the FE model and the fundamental frequency of the model was found to be 26.89 Hz. Table 2 gives the frequencies of the model for different modes.

Table 5.2: Frequencies of the confined Masonry model for different modes

Mode Number	Frequency Hz
1	26.8997
2	28.8403
3	38.7644
4	43.9416
5	59.0811
6	65.8702
7	87.5778
8	94.0157
9	102.736
10	107.888

It is to be noted that there is a close agreement in fundamental frequencies of the FE model and Experimental results.

Description	Frequencies (Hz)	
	Experimental	Analytical
Fundamental Frequency	27.50	26.89

Containment Reinforced Model 2

Model 2 was created in a similar manner as model using the FEA software. The masonry units were modeled as 4 noded shell element and the horizontal bands were modeled as 2 noded 3D beam element. The containment reinforcement was modeled as 2 noded 3D spar element. The Parameters used for modeling the FE model are summarized in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Details of model parameter for FE analysis

<i>Materi al</i>	<i>Masonry wall</i>	<i>Horizontal RC bands</i>	<i>Containment Reinforcement</i>
Eleme nt	4 noded orthotropic shell	2 noded 3D beam	2 noded 3D spar
Poisson's ratio	0	0	0
Modulus of elastici ty	1000 .00	8000.00(for 1:4 CM)	21000.00
Density kg/m³	2 0	2 5	78 00

Figure 5.8 shows the geometry of the FE model. Fig 5.9 shows the isometric view of the FE model and Fig 5.10 shows the plan view of the FE model. Fig 5.6 shows the realistic plot of Containment reinforced FE Model. Fig 5.12 to 5.14 shows the first three mode shapes of the Containment masonry model.

Figure 5.8: Geometry of FE model 2

Figure 5.9: Isometric View

Figure 5.10: Plan View

Figure 5.11: Isometric View

Figure 5.12: First Mode Shape

Figure 5.13: Second Mode Shape

Table 5.4: Frequencies of the confined Masonry model for different modes

Mode Number	Frequency Hz
1	23.0629
2	25.8134
3	36.4457
4	43.5966
5	58.9559
6	67.1648
7	77.1882
8	82.0631
9	84.1233
10	93.1810

It is to be noted that there is a close agreement in fundamental frequencies of the FE model and Experimental results.

Description	Frequencies (Hz)	
	Experimental	Analytical
Fundamental Frequency	26.50	23.062

Conclusion:

1. The major objective of the present investigation was to understand the seismic performance of confined masonry. The performance of a scaled confined masonry building model was studied using a shock table test facility. Based on the investigation, the following are the important findings.
2. The confined masonry model was able to withstand more than 150 base shocks during which local failures of some of the masonry panels beneath the sill band was noticed. Studies carried out on geometrically similar models with guide lines as recommended by IS- 4326(1993) had revealed that it could withstand about 30 base shocks during which huge portions below the lintel band collapsed. Hence it may be concluded that confined masonry is superior in performance under lateral dynamic loads.
3. Due to the mechanical bond between masonry and the confining RC elements (provided by toothed joints) no separation was observed until --- shocks. It is, hence, important to see that a continuous vertical interface between RC and masonry is avoided.

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